

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the topic of socio-psychological aspects of innovative teaching. In addition, the content of the article includes the innovative process and its psychological aspects, the concept of innovative creativity, the innovative skills of professors and teachers and its nature, psychological criteria that determine creativity, social-psychological measures to increase the effectiveness of education, Pedagogical-psychological conditions of innovative teaching, motivational, cognitive, behavioral aspects of creative-innovative activity, ability to quickly adapt to new conditions, tolerance to changes are also analyzed in detail.*

Keywords: *innovation, creativity, effective education, creativity, new conditions, empathic skills, teacher-teacher, creativity, improvement, mastery, specialist, innovation, integration.*

Introduction: Currently, a new educational system has been created in our sovereign country, through which the youth are striving to enter the world's educational space. This is a process related to serious changes in the educational process. Because the conditions of education have changed, its content has been radically renewed, and new attitudes and new views have appeared. Based on the demands of society, in providing education to the next generation, a thorough study of the content of innovative and creative activities of teachers has become one of the most important issues facing our society.

During the rapid development of science and technology, the flow of information has increased, and the main task of educational institutions is the formation of the mental abilities of a person, the improvement of creativity and innovation capabilities, as well as the development of superior abilities and talents. In our opinion, in today's educational environment, the unceasing curiosity and effectiveness of creative, innovative pedagogues, together with the necessary innovation, is not without possibility. Therefore, it is increasingly necessary to organize education according to the abilities of each learner, to create the most important socio-psychological conditions that serve their independent thinking, inquisitiveness, and creativity. Because the organization of the educational process at the level of the state educational standard requires the introduction of new pedagogical and psychological methods.

Methods: One of the tasks of the employees of the education sector is the regular psychological improvement of teaching methods, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, and the development of new educational tools. At the moment, every professor and teacher is conducting high-quality and interesting classes using their innovative and creative methods. If we take a comprehensive look at the concept of "innovation" in the context of psychological research, many scientists have given it different definitions. For example, E. Rogers explains the concept of innovation as follows: "Innovation is an idea that is new for a specific person" [1,17]. S.R. Yagolkovsky says: "Innovation is a special situation of new changes, from which we expect the fulfillment of our systemic tasks and new solutions" [2,97].

Due to its social importance, innovative phenomena began to spread widely in the field of education in the 80-85 years of the last century. As a rule, innovation appears in the situation of

several urgent problems, and it is recognized as a phenomenon that leads to the constant modernization of a psychological phenomenon, which is strictly oriented to the solution of new goals. According to V.Y.E.Klochko and E.V.Galajinskyi, a concept close to innovation, the word "Renovation" is also distinguished, it means repairing an outdated idea, integrating it into a new situation, bringing changes, and discovering new qualities, from the old. is characterized by such things as moving away [3,82]. According to many famous representatives of the social sphere, "Innovation, the innovative-creative process is noted as a type of activity of educational institutions related to the creation of news, acquisition of knowledge, its application and dissemination in the conditions of changes. For example, L.A. Regush emphasizes in his research that "innovation" is reflected in the content of knowledge, methodology, technology, organization of educational work, effective management of the educational system, etc. [4,123]. E.I. In her research, Mesheryakova singled out the following features of using innovative teaching methods in the educational process [5,69-75]:

Self-education technology increases the social and psychological responsibility of a person and forms virtues and moral qualities for mastering the basics of science during the educational process.

- Mastering the laws of society and nature on the basis of integration;
- A new ability that came to life on the basis of creative research unknown to the teacher;
- The content and methods of teaching in differentiated step-by-step educational technology are aimed at forming an individual's innovative ability on the basis of creative research and action.

- Information programming education - organization of educational content from the point of view of interdisciplinary communication;

- Systematic conscious culture is formed in the harmonious worldview of "man-society-nature" in illustrative and explanatory teaching;

- In the humanization of technology, the application of advanced scientific innovations of psychology from the point of view of "child-subject", and "child-object" is considered appropriate for the current purpose. Scientific knowledge is considered in the unity of life situations and social situations. Three types of innovation can be found in advanced works on educational management: modification innovation, combinatory innovation, and radical innovation. Below we will try to clarify the content of these three concepts.

Modification innovation is the development of something that already exists, changing its form. For example, V.F. Shatalov's mathematics scheme and its use by many teachers in the educational process is a clear example. Combinative modification is a new construction of previously unused, known stylistic elements. Radical innovation is an approach that advocates oldness and immutability, and by now this component is not recognized by many scientists. However, there are also types of societies that support this type of innovation. According to M. V. Klarin, national innovation is the introduction of new state standards in education [6,56]. The state standard in education mainly forms the quantity, conditions, level, and quality indicators of education.

Results: Today, thanks to the many opportunities offered by a number of educational institutions in our country, organizations are able to provide services according to any model. In this direction, various types of new ideas, and new technologies based on educational content, structure, science, and experience have been developed. Therefore, based on the age and individual

psychological characteristics of each learner, it is very important to choose different teaching technologies and educational content and test them in practice. According to V. A. Abchuk's work "Management for Pedagogical Field Specialties", the implementation of innovative processes in education is determined by three interrelated conditions[7,88]:

1. With the characteristics of the implemented technology;
2. With the innovative potential of innovators;
3. Methods of introducing innovation, etc.

New innovative teaching technology is a special type of professional activity. In order to master the innovative technology of teaching, it will be necessary to mobilize a great pedagogical experience. This is a job that requires creativity and entrepreneurial, creative qualities. In fact, every teacher develops and shapes himself in the process of mastering new innovative technology. In the 21st century, the issues of professionally advanced training of future specialists and the formation of their innovative and creative qualities are considered very important tasks.

According to the conclusions of S.N. Tolstov, the training of future specialists with new innovative and creative qualities and the use of advanced methods includes the following [8,50]:

The motivational aspect - includes the formation of cognitive interests, it is the professional formation of future specialists, increasing their valuable attitude to science, striving for professional development, and awakening special love for the future profession, it is reflected in teaching the teacher to feel that he is in a leading position in the education of the future generation, and directing him to further increase his level.

- The cognitive aspect is the level of general cultural training and meaningful methodological training of future specialists, their knowledge of the specialty, a single effective educational system, the psychological laws of mastering and creation, and the forces that serve to acquire knowledge and skills. includes. In addition, effective education includes the theoretical foundations of the process and the mastering of the scientific foundations of mastering and creativity, knowing the basics of creative activity, and being able to feel creativity. The ability of a future specialist to adapt to any situation is called flexibility.

- The aspect of innovation and creativity is distinguished by the future specialist's ability to quickly recognize the social and professional environment, the use of effective methods of professional self-awareness, and interest in innovative pedagogical technologies. This includes knowing the social and professional environment of the future specialist, being able to apply professional knowledge in his practice, and studying and learning innovative pedagogical technologies.

- The professional motivational aspect is measured by the future specialist's ability to determine the goals and tasks of his professional activity and effectively implement the process of pedagogical communication. It is characterized by the future specialist's thorough mastery of his subject, knowledge of the psychological and pedagogical foundations of the overall educational process, and the ability to plan and implement the pedagogical process. Innovative and creative skills in education are also determined by the methodological goals of teaching, the advanced teaching process, the ability to define its tasks, the ability to predict the results of teaching and the acquisition of socio-psychological knowledge that is considered necessary for leadership. It is very important for a future specialist to be able to effectively organize a lesson in a holistic educational process, to be able to establish cooperation with students, to be able to diagnose group relations, and to be able to choose effective psychological methods to prevent conflicts.

According to V. P. Delia, innovative and creative qualities include creative thinking, creative activity, creative inquisitiveness, tolerance in adapting to educational conditions, and the empathetic attitude of a future specialist. At the same time, it includes the ability of a future specialist to independently analyze scientific and research work, strive to increase and improve his knowledge, use innovative methods, introduce unique innovations and changes, and creatively use innovation. takes [9,57].

Conclusion: In general, the innovative and creative activity of professors in higher education is reflected in the following:

- The ability to change, improve, and better perceive the innovative experience of others, taking into account one's own experience;
- The need to be aware of new scientific ideas and the experience of others, to understand the results of one's own work;
- New scientific research, the ability to methodically apply them with continuous practice;
- Experience in independently creating new teaching methods and tools;
- Ability to actively fight against professional deformation, various dogmas, and professional backwardness.
- Ability to ensure the effectiveness of the teaching, learning and mastering process;
- Ability to ensure the unity of requirements and wishes of the participants of the educational process;
- Forming a person's creative ability and creativity;
- To always be an innovator in professional activities, to be tolerant in mutual relations, to be able to quickly adapt to new conditions, etc.

Timely development of these noted qualities, development of a scientific psychological model of its implementation, timely support of creative, innovative, creative qualities of a person, and extensive research of them from a socio-psychological point of view, if the current society remains, It is the most urgent, social and economic issue facing modern psychology.

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